

Academic Research and Publishing Skills

Dr Mark Perkins
2023

Research Skills 1

Literature Search

Google Search

Google Scholar

Web of Science

The State of Knowledge

Find relevant journals

Find relevant articles

Compile lists of authors

Compile bibliographies

Be aware of the research

Don't re-invent the wheel!

google

[All](#) [Videos](#) [News](#) [Images](#) [Maps](#) [More](#) [Tools](#)

About 9,900,000,000 results (0.66 seconds)

<https://www.google.co.uk>

Google

Search the world's information, including webpages, images, videos and more. Google has many special features to help you find exactly what you're looking ...

Google Maps

Find local businesses, view maps and get driving directions in ...

[More results from google.co.uk »](#)

Top stories

Forbes
Google Confirms
Massive Upgrade For

Mashable
Pixel 6 and 6 Pro review:
The 'Google phone' that

EveningNews
X-rated pose from
woman caught on

Google

Technology company

Google LLC is an American multinational technology company that specializes in Internet-related services and products, which include online advertising technologies, a search engine, cloud computing, software, and hardware. [Wikipedia](#)

CEO: Sundar Pichai (2 Oct 2015–) [Trending](#)

Founded: 4 September 1998, Menlo Park, California, United States

Headquarters: Mountain View, California, United States

Revenue: 181.7 billion USD (2020)

Subsidiaries: YouTube, Kaggle, Fitbit, Google AdMob, Dialogflow, MORE

About 2,360,000,000 results (0.65 seconds)

Ads - Shop philosophy of mind

Philosophy of Mind: A Comprehensive... £20.99 Amazon.co.uk By Google

Philosophy of Mind: A Very Short... £7.34 Amazon.co.uk By Google

The Philosophy of Mind By Peter Smith £3.79 Used World of Books By Google

Philosophy of Mind: Classical and... £14.82 Used AbeBooks.co.uk By Klarna

Philosophy of mind

Field of study

Philosophy of mind is a branch of philosophy that studies the ontology and nature of the mind and its relationship with the body. Wikipedia

People also search for View 10+ more

Scholarly articles for philosophy of mind

Philosophy of mind - Kim - Cited by 1842

An introduction to the philosophy of mind - Lowe - Cited by 306

An introduction to the philosophy of mind - Martin - Cited by 156

Google Scholar

- Find Citations

Stand on the shoulders of giants.

Google Scholar provides a simple way to broadly search for scholarly literature. From one place, you can search across many disciplines and sources: articles, theses, books, abstracts and court opinions, from academic publishers, professional societies, online repositories, universities and other web sites. Google Scholar helps you find relevant work across the world of scholarly research.

Features of Google Scholar

- Search all scholarly literature from one convenient place
- Explore related works, citations, authors, and publications
- Locate the complete document through your library or on the web
- Keep up with recent developments in any area of research
- Check who's citing your publications, create a public author profile

Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus:

Which is best for me?

LSE blog December 2019

- Google Scholar found most citations to Social Sciences articles (94%)
- Web of Science and Scopus found 35% / 43%

- Google Scholar appeared to be a superset of Web of Science and Scopus

- The majority (~60%) of the citations found only by Google Scholar come from non-journal sources
- Theses and dissertations
- Books and book chapters
- in formally published papers such as preprints and working papers (especially important in Business and Economics)
- Conference papers

<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2019/12/03/google-scholar-web-of-science-and-scopus-which-is-best-for-me/>

Google Scholar

Articles About 3,150,000 results (0.07 sec) My profile My library

Any time

Since 2022

Since 2021

Since 2018

Custom range...

Sort by relevance

Sort by date

Any type

Review articles

include patents

include citations

Create alert

book **Philosophy of mind**
 J Kim - 2018 - taylorfrancis.com
 ... Collectively called "the **mind-body problem**," this has been a central problem of **philosophy of mind** since Descartes introduced it nearly four centuries ago. It is a central problem for us in this book as well. The task here is to clarify and make intelligible the relation between our ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 1842 Related articles All 5 versions ⓘ

book **An introduction to the philosophy of mind**
 E.J. Lowe - 2000 - books.google.com
 In this book Jonathan Lowe offers a lucid and wide-ranging introduction to the **philosophy of mind**. Using a problem-centred approach designed to stimulate as well as instruct, he begins with a general examination of the **mind-body problem** and moves on to detailed ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 306 Related articles All 3 versions ⓘ

An introduction to the philosophy of mind
 K Maslin - 2001 - philpapers.org
 2nd edition of this well respected and popular introduction to the **philosophy of mind** fully updated and expanded throughout includes a new chapter which explores Aristotiles **philosophy of psychology and mind** designed to help students think for themselves and contains ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 158 Related articles All 3 versions ⓘ

book **Philosophy of mind: A contemporary introduction** [DOC] utm.edu
 J Heil - 2012 - taylorfrancis.com
 ... or no background in **philosophy** to central issues in the **philosophy of mind**, and to do ...
philosophy of mind and various empirical domains: psychology, neuroscience, and artificial intelligence, for instance. It is not that I regard empirical work as irrelevant to the **philosophy of mind** ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 417 Related articles All 10 versions ⓘ

Related searches

philosophy of mind epistemology	empiricism philosophy of mind
contemporary philosophy of mind	philosophy of mind consciousness
cognitive science philosophy of mind	philosophy of mind neuroscience
philosophy of mind metaphysics	philosophy of mind psychology

book **Philosophy of mind: An introduction**
 G Graham - 1993 - pdfs.semanticscholar.org
 Now a day those who Living in the era just where everything reachable by connect to the internet and the resources included can be true or not need people to be aware of each facts

Google Scholar philosophy of mind free download

Articles About 715,000 results (0.09 sec) My profile My library

Any time
 Since 2022
 Since 2021
 Since 2018
 Custom range...

Sort by relevance
 Sort by date

Any type
 Review articles
 include patents
 include citations
 Create alert

book **Philosophy of mind: An introduction**
 G Graham - 1993 - pdfs.semanticscholar.org
 Spent a **free** time to be fun actively to perform! A lot of people spent their down time with their family, or their friends. Usually they ... Do you need to something different to fill your current **free** time/ holiday? Could possibly be reading a book may be option to fill your no cost time! ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 144 Related articles All 3 versions ⓘ

book **Introducing philosophy: A text with integrated readings** [PDF] aeronauticalelectric.com
 RC Solomon, KM Higgins, [C W Martin](#) - 2001 - aeronauticalelectric.com
 ... **Mind** you that your students are affected by reading this book. The ... of **philosophy** and the many ways in which they are, and have been, answered. The authors combine substantial selections from significant works in the history of **philosophy** with excerpts from current **philosophy** ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 148 Related articles All 5 versions ⓘ

book **Philosophy: The quest for truth** [PDF] happydays.gr
 LP Fogman, L Vaughn - 2006 - happydays.gr
 The Quest For Truth Popular **Download Philosophy** The Quest For Truth Full Collection, **Free Download Philosophy** The Quest For ... Coat **free** of popo superior indicates like i carry it to room dc since we last 76 years old but where people argument from daily life on me ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 65 Related articles All 5 versions ⓘ

book **The liberal mind**
 K Minogue - 2012 - muse.jhu.edu
 Kenneth Minogue offers a brilliant and provocative exploration of liberalism in the Western world today: its roots and its influences, its present state, and its prospects in the new century. The **Liberal Mind** limns the taxonomy of a way of thinking that constitutes the very ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 197 Related articles ⓘ

book **Questions that matter: An invitation to philosophy** [PDF] kirjastot.fi
 ELR Miller, J Jensen - 1993 - kirjastot.fi
 ... had a touch of **mind** over and over and over but the colorful mentality of our lives he is from his first father. Barbara 's guidelines pattern plates and source errors and tips for the symbol ... Most of it posted twists with what a great read to keep teachers who have no problem with ...
 ☆ Save ⓘ Cite Cited by 155 Related articles All 2 versions ⓘ

Philosophy of mind and human nature
 R Pasnau - 2011 - philpapers.org
 A theory of human nature must consider from the start whether it sees human beings in fundamentally biological terms, as animals like other animals, or else in fundamentally supernatural terms, as creatures of God who are like God in some special way, and so importantly ...

Google Scholar philosophy of mind free g e l owen

Articles About 11,600 results (0.15 sec) My profile My library

Any time
 Since 2022
 Since 2021
 Since 2018
 Custom range ...

Sort by relevance
 Sort by date

Any type
 Review articles

include patents
 include citations

Create alert

Plato and Parmenides on the timeless present
 GEL Owen - The Monist, 1966 - pdcnet.org
 Some statements couched in the present tense have no reference to time. They are, if you like, gram. matically tensed but logically tenseless. Mathematical statements such as "twice two is four" or "there is a prime number between 125 and 128" are of this sort. So is the statement ...
 ☆ Save Cite Cited by 167 Related articles All 6 versions

Eleatic questions
 GEL Owen - The classical quarterly, 1960 - cambridge.org
 ... GEL OWEN brunt of his opening argument to proving that his subject is temporally infinite, whereas its spatial infinity—supposedly the major point of departure from Parmenides—is introduced by the almost perfunctory dAA' woiwp ecmv del, OVTCO Kal TO yiAyedos dneipov ...
 ☆ Save Cite Cited by 315 Related articles All 6 versions

The place of the Timaeus in Plato's dialogues
 GEL Owen - The Classical Quarterly, 1953 - cambridge.org
 ... Its thesis could have been supported otherwise, by showing how the Parmenides and its successors gain in philosophical power and interest when they are read as following and not as paving the way for the Timaeus; here I want only to find grounds for this approach. And it ...
 ☆ Save Cite Cited by 344 Related articles All 5 versions

What is Philosophy?
 P.W. Rosemann - Philotheos, 2017 - pdcnet.org
 Toward the beginning of the Symposium, we find Socrates and his friend Aristodemus headed to a banquet at Agathon's. Socrates is looking forward to the event. He had avoided Agathon's victory feast the day before because he was afraid of "the crowd" (τόν ὄχλον, 174a), the ...
 ☆ Save Cite All 11 versions

Aristotle's psychology
 C Shields - 2000 - plato.stanford.edu
 Moreover, because of its evident affinities with some prominent approaches in contemporary philosophy of mind, Aristotle's psychology has received renewed interest and has incited intense interpretative dispute in recent decades. Consequently, this entry proceeds on two ...
 ☆ Save Cite Cited by 155 Related articles All 2 versions

Paul Hamlyn "There must be another way..."
 P Jarvis, S Thomson - Logos, 2003 - philpapers.org
 ... The Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Edited by Paul Edwards, The Macmillan Company & The Free Press, New York, and Collier-Macmillan ... The Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Edited by Paul Edwards, The Macmillan Company & The Free Press, New York, and Collier-Macmillan ...
 ☆ Save Cite All 2 versions

[PDF] academia.edu

[PDF] maynoothuniversity.ie

[HTML] stanford.edu

CAMBRIDGE
UNIVERSITY PRESS

Eleatic Questions

Author(s): G. E. L. Owen

Source: *The Classical Quarterly*, May, 1960, Vol. 10, No. 1 (May, 1960), pp. 84-102

Published by: Cambridge University Press on behalf of The Classical Association

Stable URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/637593>

JSTOR is a not-for-profit service that helps scholars, researchers, and students discover, use, and build upon a wide range of content in a trusted digital archive. We use information technology and tools to increase productivity and facilitate new forms of scholarship. For more information about JSTOR, please contact support@jstor.org.
Your use of the JSTOR archive indicates your acceptance of the Terms & Conditions of Use, available at <https://about.jstor.org/terms>

Where are the Journals?

- Ebscohost
- Scopus
 - Scopus is the largest abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature: scientific journals, books and conference proceedings
- PLOS
 - Public library of science
- CORE
 - “The world’s largest collection of open access research papers”
 - 179m

<https://www.ebsco.com/>

https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/15534/supporthub/scopus/#tip

[s](https://plos.org/)

<https://plos.org/>

<https://core.ac.uk/>

<https://arxiv.org/>

[Home](#)[News](#)[About](#)[Support](#)[FAQ](#)[Feedback](#)[Access now](#)

[Connect](#) to the Web of Science Service.

About the Web of Science Service for UK Education

The **Web of Science Service for UK Education** provides a single route of access to Clarivate Analytics' products subscribed to by an individual institution.

It includes **Web of Science Core Collection**, **Journal Citation Reports**, **Current Contents Connect**, **Derwent Innovations Index** and many others. This platform provides a unique way of searching, including the ability to perform an 'All Databases' search on the content of multiple searchable products.

Please choose below to jump directly to any one of the following sections:

- [Subscription and Pricing](#)
- [Within the Web of Science Platform](#)
- [Additional Products](#)

Subscription and Pricing

Links to the available Jisc agreements can be found on the following Licence Subscriptions Manager (just enter 'Clarivate Analytics' into the search bar): <https://subscriptionsmanager.jisc.ac.uk/>.

For non-UK academic institutions and individual user requests, please [contact Clarivate Analytics directly](#) for information on alternative access to their products.

For details of current subscribers to the Web of Science Service for UK Education, please see the [current list of licensed institutions](#).

[Back to top ^](#)

Within the Web of Science Platform

The basic databases available are:

<https://wok.mimas.ac.uk/>

Already have a manuscript?

Use our Manuscript Matcher to find the best relevant journals!

Find a Match

Filters

Clear All

- Web of Science Coverage
- Open Access
- Category
- Country / Region
- Language
- Frequency
- Journal Citation Reports

Refine Your Search Results

ancient philosophy

Search

Sort By: Relevancy

Search Results

Found 735 results (Page 1)

Share These Results

Did you mean this journal?

SCHOLE-FILOSOFSKOE ANTIKOVEDENIE I KLASSICHESKAYA TRADITSIYA-SCHOLE-ANCIENT PHILOSOPHY AND THE CLASSICAL TRADITION

Publisher: NOVOSIBIRSK STATE UNIV, UL PIROGOVA, DOM 2, NOVOSIBIRSK, RUSSIA, 630090

ISSN / eISSN: 1995-4328 / 1995-4336

Web of Science Core Collection: Emerging Sources Citation Index

Share This Journal

View profile page

*Requires free login.

Other Possible Matches

APEIRON-A JOURNAL FOR ANCIENT PHILOSOPHY AND SCIENCE

Frequency

Journal Citation Reports

Requires free login

Other Possible Matches

APEIRON-A JOURNAL FOR ANCIENT PHILOSOPHY AND SCIENCE

Publisher: **WALTER DE GRUYTER GMBH , GENTHINER STRASSE 13, BERLIN, GERMANY, D-10785**

ISSN / eISSN: **0003-6390 / 2156-7093**

Web of Science Core Collection: **Emerging Sources Citation Index**

[Share This Journal](#)

[View profile page](#)

* Requires free login.

PHRONESIS-A JOURNAL FOR ANCIENT PHILOSOPHY

Publisher: **BRILL , PLANTIJN STRAAT 2, P O BOX 9000, LEIDEN, NETHERLANDS, 2300 PA**

ISSN / eISSN: **0031-8868 / 1568-5284**

Web of Science Core Collection: **Arts & Humanities Citation Index**

Additional Web of Science Indexes: **Current Contents Arts & Humanities**

[Share This Journal](#)

[View profile page](#)

* Requires free login.

RHIZOMATA-A JOURNAL FOR ANCIENT PHILOSOPHY AND SCIENCE

Publisher: **WALTER DE GRUYTER GMBH , GENTHINER STRASSE 13, BERLIN, GERMANY, D-10785**

ISSN / eISSN: **2196-5102 / 2196-5110**

Web of Science Core Collection: **Emerging Sources Citation Index**

About EBSCO

EBSCO is the leading provider of research databases, e-journals, magazine subscriptions, e-books and discovery service to libraries of all kinds. For more than 70 years, we've partnered with libraries to improve research with quality content and technology.

An industry leader

EBSCO Information Services is a division of **EBSCO Industries, Inc.**, one of the largest privately held and family-owned companies in the United States. EBSCO Industries, Inc. has been in business since 1944. Starting out as a small subscription agency, EBSCO quickly became a pioneer in the library services industry.

Through vision, action and innovation, EBSCO invests in the library business to ensure the long-term growth of products, services and technologies for our customers.

From research, acquisition management, subscription services and discovery to clinical decision support and patient care, learning, and research and development, EBSCO provides libraries, health care and medical institutions, corporations and government agencies with access to content and resources to serve the information and workflow needs of their users and organizations.

[Learn more about our industry expertise](#)

EBSCOhost Research Platform

EBSCOhost is an intuitive online research platform used by thousands of institutions and millions of users worldwide. With quality databases and search features, EBSCOhost helps researchers of all kinds find the information they need fast.

Start your research

Why EBSCOhost for research?

Basic and advanced search options

EBSCOhost serves both new and experienced researchers with a variety of features to refine search results.

Customization

Modify EBSCOhost interface branding and features, including search limiters and expanders, language preferences, print options, link options and more. Use [EBSCO apps](#) to further enhance your EBSCOhost experience.

Reliable, peer-reviewed content

EBSCOhost offers high-quality articles licensed from reputable publishers recognized by library professionals, chosen to meet the specific needs of researchers.

Ebscohost

Mobile access

EBSCOhost recognizes when users are accessing the site from a smartphone or tablet and will display a mobile-friendly version.

Why EBSCOhost for research?

✓ Basic and advanced search options

EBSCOhost serves both new and experienced researchers with a variety of features to refine search results.

✓ Reliable, peer-reviewed content

EBSCOhost offers high-quality articles licensed from reputable publishers recognized by library professionals, chosen to meet the specific needs of researchers.

✓ Citation assistance

Users can view, save, print, email or export citations in many formats directly from the database.

✓ Ability to save searches and results

Users can save searches and articles in a password-protected folder for later reference.

✓ Customization

Modify EBSCOhost interface branding and features, including search limiters and expanders, language preferences, print options, link options and more. Use [EBSCO apps](#) to further enhance your EBSCOhost experience.

✓ Mobile access

EBSCOhost recognizes when users are accessing the site from a smartphone or tablet and will display a mobile-friendly version.

✓ Accessibility

EBSCOhost features text-to-speech for HTML articles, ARIA landmarks and more. [Read more about accessibility.](#)

✓ Privacy

COPPA compliance means EBSCO does not ask for or require personal information to access its databases.

Scopus

- Scopus is the largest abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature: scientific journals, books and conference proceedings.
- Delivering a comprehensive overview of the world's research output in the fields of science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and arts and humanities, Scopus features smart tools to track, analyze and visualize research.

Scopus: Access and use Support Center

[Support Center](#) > [Scopus: Access and use Support Center](#) > [Access](#) > [What is Scopus Preview?](#)

All Topics ▾ Search

[Orders & Renewals](#)

[Access](#)

[Onboarding](#)

[Training](#)

[Using the product](#)

[Content](#)

[New and updated FAQs](#)

What is Scopus Preview?

Last updated on July 29, 2021

Scopus offers free features to non-subscribed users and is available through Scopus Preview.

Researchers may use Scopus Preview to assist with their research, such as searching authors, and learning more about Scopus content coverage and source metrics.

Scopus is the largest abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature: scientific journals, books and conference proceedings. Delivering a comprehensive overview of the world's research output in the fields of science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and arts and humanities, Scopus features smart tools to track, analyze and visualize research.

For more information, see [What is Scopus about?](#)

What can you do through Scopus Preview?

Note that article search and some other features (such as sorting functions, etc.) are only available to our subscribed customers. You can [check access](#) ↗ or contact the administrator of your institution to [find out how you may be eligible for full Scopus access](#).

Welcome to Scopus Preview

[What is Scopus](#) [Blog](#)

Check whether you can access Scopus remotely through your institution

[Maybe later](#) [Check access](#)

Check access

Check if you have access through your sign in credentials or via your institution.

[Check Scopus access](#)

Check out your free author profile!

Did you know Scopus offers free profiles to all indexed authors? Review yours, claim it, and update it — all for free!

[View your author profile](#)

Scopus content

[Content coverage guide](#)

[Scopus source list](#)

[Book title list](#)

[Scopus discontinued sources list](#)

Looking for free journal rankings and metrics?

Scopus offers free metrics to non-subscribers.

[View journal rankings](#)

Don't have a Scopus account?

You can [create an account](#) for free access to Scopus preview and other Elsevier products.

Interested in subscribing to Scopus?

[Contact sales](#) to speak with your local representative.

What can you do through Scopus Preview?

Note that article search and some other features (such as sorting functions, etc.) are only available to our subscribed customers. You can [check access](#) or contact the administrator of your institution to find out how you may be eligible for full Scopus access.

Feature	Explanation
Scopus Sources	Scopus Preview provides access to Scopus Sources, but not the Source Comparison tool
Author details	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Review author details• Request corrections to your author profile• Add author details to ORCID <p>Note: When using Scopus Preview, the Author ID is displayed in the URL (web address) of the author's profile page.</p>
CiteScore	You have complete transparency over Scopus CiteScore when you create a user account.

For more information about registering, see [How do I register with Scopus?](#)

For information about signing into Scopus Preview, see [How to sign in to Scopus Preview?](#)

Global Representation means global discovery Across all subjects and content types

Number of journals by subject area**

Physical sciences
13,525

Health sciences
14,583

Social sciences
12,837

Life sciences
7,379

Journals

24,272
Peer-reviewed Journals

270
Trade journals

5,859
Active gold open access journals

>8,000
Articles in press

Full metadata, abstracts and cited references

Conference

101K
Conference events

10.2M
Conference papers

Mainly Engineering, mathematics, physics and computer sciences

Books

60K
Volumes

788
Books series

1.9M
Items

230,000+
Stand-alone books

Mainly social sciences and arts & humanities

Scopus includes content from more than 5,000 publishers and 105 different countries

- 40 different languages covered
- Updated daily
- Multiple regional content types covered (journals, conferences, books, book series)
- 10.6M open access documents

* Numbers as of August 2020. ** Journals may be in multiple subject areas

About Us

The SCImago Journal & Country Rank is a publicly available portal that includes the journals and country scientific indicators developed from the information contained in the [Scopus®](#) database ([Elsevier B.V.](#)). These indicators can be used to assess and analyze scientific domains. Journals can be compared or analysed separately. Country rankings may also be compared or analysed separately. Journals can be grouped by subject area (27 major thematic areas), subject category (309 specific subject categories) or by country. Citation data is drawn from over 34,100 titles from more than 5,000 international publishers and country performance metrics from 239 countries worldwide. The SJCR allows you also to embed significant journal metrics into your web as a clickable image widget

This platform takes its name from the [SCImago Journal Rank \(SJR\) indicator](#) (PDF), developed by SCImago from the widely known algorithm [Google PageRank™](#). This indicator shows the visibility of the journals contained in the [Scopus®](#) database from 1996.

[SCImago](#) is a research group from the Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), University of Granada, Extremadura, Carlos III (Madrid) and Alcalá de Henares, dedicated to information analysis, representation and retrieval by means of visualisation techniques.

As well as the SJR Portal, SCImago has developed [The Shape of Science](#), the [SIR \(SCImago Institution Rankings\)](#) and the [Atlas of Science](#). The Shape of Science is an information visualization project whose aim is to reveal the structure of science. Its interface has been designed to access the bibliometric indicators database of the SCImago Journal & Country Rank portal. The SIR is a classification of academic and research-related institutions ranked by a composite indicator that combines three different sets of indicators based on research performance, innovation outputs and societal impact measured by their web visibility. The Atlas of Science project proposes the creation of an information system whose major aim is to achieve a graphic representation of IberoAmerican Science Research. Such representation is conceived as a collection of interactive maps, allowing navigation functions throughout the semantic spaces formed by the maps.

Contact e-mail: contact@scimago.es

[How to cite this website](#)

All subject areas

All subject categories

All regions / countries

All types

2021

Only Open Access Journals Only SciELO Journals Only WoS Journals

Display journals with at least 0

Citable Docs. (3years)

Apply

Download data

1 - 50 of 27339

	Title	Type	SJR	H index	Total Docs. (2021)	Total Docs. (3years)	Total Refs. (2021)	Total Cites (3years)	Citable Docs. (3years)	Cites / Doc. (2years)	Ref. / Doc. (2021)	
1	Nature	journal	17.897 Q1	1276	2506	8299	54378	160609	3834	21.05	21.70	
2	Science	journal	14.589 Q1	1229	2994	9322	47391	143184	4215	15.19	15.83	
3	New England Journal of Medicine	journal	24.907 Q1	1079	1453	4498	14767	143343	1891	35.41	10.16	
4	Cell	journal	25.716 Q1	814	517	1727	33658	73240	1639	45.00	65.10	
5	Lancet, The	journal	15.652 Q1	807	1377	4587	22640	85917	1226	22.23	16.44	

Psychology All subject categories All regions / countries All types 2021

Only Open Access Journals Only SciELO Journals Only WoS Journals ? Display journals with at least 0 Citable Docs. (3years) Apply

Download data

1 - 50 of 1323 < >

	Title	Type	SJR	H index	Total Docs. (2021)	Total Docs. (3years)	Total Refs. (2021)	Total Cites (3years)	Citable Docs. (3years)	Cites / Doc. (2years)	Ref. / Doc. (2021)	
1	Journal of Personality and Social Psychology	journal	3.697 Q1	392	135	384	13260	3064	375	7.19	98.22	
2	Psychological Bulletin	journal	7.504 Q1	328	43	121	8754	2664	114	21.28	203.58	
3	Trends in Cognitive Sciences	journal	6.222 Q1	326	133	359	9071	5121	297	13.65	68.20	
4	Journal of Applied Psychology	journal	6.445 Q1	306	181	250	20097	2810	249	10.71	111.03	
5	Psychological Science	journal	3.020 Q1	277	167	494	6220	3666	449	7.29	37.25	

FIND SIMILAR JOURNALS

options

1 Current Directions in Psychological Science USA 79% similarity	2 Perspectives on Psychological Science USA 79% similarity	3 Psychological Science USA 77% similarity	4 Current Opinion in Psychology GBR 70% similarity
--	--	--	--

Ads by Google

[Stop seeing this ad](#) [Why this ad?](#)

Sources

Subject area

Subject: Philosophy x

Improved Citescore

We have updated the CiteScore methodology to ensure a more robust, stable and comprehensive metric which provides an indication of research impact, earlier. The updated methodology will be applied to the calculation of CiteScore, as well as retroactively for all previous CiteScore years (i.e. 2018, 2017, 2016...). The previous CiteScore values have been removed and are no longer available. [View CiteScore methodology.](#)

Filter refine list

Apply Clear filters

Display options

Display only Open Access Journals

Counts for 4-year timeframe

No minimum selected

Minimum citations

Minimum documents

CiteScore highest quartile

Show only titles in top 10 percent

805 results

[Download Scopus Source List](#) [Learn more about Scopus Source List](#)

All

View metrics for year: 2020

Source title ↓	CiteScore ↓	Highest percentile ↓	Citations 2017-20 ↓	Documents 2017-20 ↓	% Cited ↓
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Political Psychology	7.1	99% 1/644 Philosophy	2,144	302	78
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2 Philosophy and Technology	6.3	99% 2/644 Philosophy	759	120	75
<input type="checkbox"/> 3 International Journal of Social Robotics	6.2	99%	1,391	224	83

Research Skills 1

Researching Articles - 1

- Look in a particular journal
 - MDPI
- Orcid
- Preprints

Search:

Journals / Philosophies

philosophies

Journal Menu

- [Philosophies Home](#)
- [Aims & Scope](#)
- [Editorial Board](#)
- [Reviewer Board](#)
- [Topical Advisory Panel](#)
- [Instructions for Authors](#)
- [Special Issues](#)

Are the winners lucky?

Philosophies

Philosophies is an international, peer-reviewed, open access journal promoting re-integration of diverse forms of philosophical reflection and scientific research on fundamental issues in science, technology and culture, published bimonthly online by MDPI.

- **Open Access** — free for readers, with article processing charges (APC) paid by authors or their institutions.

E-Mail Alert

Add your e-mail address to receive forthcoming issues of this journal:

News

22 November 2021
721 MDPI Editorial Board Members Receiving "2021 Highly Cited Researchers" Distinction

(This article belongs to the Special Issue From the Acquisition of Knowledge to the Promotion of Wisdom)

Open Access Article

Induction, Experimentation and Causation in the Social Sciences

by Lars-Göran Johansson

Philosophies 2021, 6(4), 105; <https://doi.org/10.3390/philosophies6040105> - 16 Dec 2021

Viewed by 420

Abstract Inductive thinking is a universal human habit; we generalise from our experiences the best we can. The induction problem is to identify which observed regularities provide reasonable justification for inductive conclusions. In the natural sciences, we can often use strict laws in making [...] [Read more.](#)

(This article belongs to the Special Issue The Problem of Induction throughout the Philosophy of Science)

[► Show Figures](#)

Open Access Correction

Correction: Tantlevskij et al. Network Analysis of the Interaction between Different Religious and Philosophical Movements in Early Judaism. *Philosophies* 2021, 6, 2

by Igor R. Tantlevskij, Ekaterina V. Gromova and Dmitry Gromov

Philosophies 2021, 6(4), 104; <https://doi.org/10.3390/philosophies6040104> - 16 Dec 2021

Viewed by 300

[Back to Top](#)

philosophies

Submit to this Journal

Review for this Journal

Edit a Special Issue

Article Menu

Article Overview

- Abstract
- Open Access and Permissions
- Share and Cite
- Article Metrics
- Related Articles
- Order Article Reprints

Open Access Article

Induction, Experimentation and Causation in the Social Sciences

by Lars-Göran Johansson ^{1,2}

¹ Department of Philosophy, Uppsala University, P.O. Box 256, 751 05 Uppsala, Sweden

² Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, 106 91 Stockholm, Sweden

Academic Editors: Marcin J. Schroeder and Benjamin Jantzen

Philosophies **2021**, *6*(4), 105; <https://doi.org/10.3390/philosophies6040105>

Received: 21 July 2021 / Revised: 4 December 2021 / Accepted: 9 December 2021 /

Published: 16 December 2021

(This article belongs to the Special Issue *The Problem of Induction throughout the Philosophy of Science*)

[View Full-Text](#)

[Download PDF](#)

[Browse Figure](#)

[Review Reports](#)

[Citation Export](#)

Abstract Views 423

Full-Text Views 321

Preprints

READ,
SHARE &
COMMENT

Abstract

Inductive thinking is a universal human habit; we generalise from our experiences the best we can. The induction problem is to identify which observed regularities provide reasonable justification for inductive conclusions. In the natural sciences, we can often use strict laws in making successful inferences about unobserved states of affairs. In the social sciences, by contrast, we have no strict laws, only regularities which most often are conditioned on *ceteris paribus* clauses. This makes it much more difficult to make reliable inferences in the social sciences. In particular, we want knowledge about general causal relations in order to be able to determine what to do in order to achieve a certain state of affairs. Knowledge about causal relations that are also valid in the future requires experiments or so called 'natural experiments'. Only knowledge derived from such experiences enable us to draw reasonably reliable inferences about how to act in order to achieve our goals. [View Full-Text](#)

Keywords: induction problem; natural versus social science; complexity; causation; experimentation in social science; laws; *ceteris paribus* clauses

▼ Show Figures

Article Submission

Orcid

Submit your
paper

- Use Orcid
- 8 April 2021, the number of live accounts was 11,130,061

ORCID
stands for
Open Researcher and Contributor ID

<https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/>

EDIT PERSONAL INFORMATION

Names

First Name
David T

Last Name
Palmer

Published Name
DT Palmer

Other Names
David T Palmer; 팔머 데이비드; 파머-데이비드; 宗樹朝

About Me
Biography
David Palmer is an Associate University Librarian for Digital Strategies & Technical Services and Principal Investigator for The HKU Scholars Hub at The University of Hong Kong, where his career

Keywords

Country
Hong Kong SAR China

Websites

HKU ResearcherPage (<http://hub.hku.hk/rp/00001>)

Google Scholar Citations (<https://user=M2Nuhm0AAAA>)

ResearcherID (<http://www.rese>)

Website
Description URL

Email Address
Email

DT Palmer

<http://orcid.org/0000-0001-5616-4635>

Also known as:

David T Palmer
宗樹朝
鵬大衛
팔머 데이비드
파머-데이비드

Websites:

HKU ResearcherPage
Google Scholar Citations

Add other versions of your name here

DISTINGUISH YOURSELF IN THREE EASY STEPS

ORCID provides a persistent digital identifier that distinguishes you from every other researcher and, through integration in key research workflows such as manuscript and grant submission, supports automated linkages between you and your professional activities ensuring that your work is recognized. [Find out more.](#)

1

REGISTER

Get your unique ORCID identifier. [Register now!](#)
Registration takes 30 seconds.

2

ADD YOUR INFO

Enhance your ORCID record with your professional information and link to your other identifiers (such as Scopus or ResearcherID or LinkedIn).

3

USE YOUR ORCID ID

Include your ORCID identifier on your Webpage, when you submit publications, apply for grants, and in any research workflow to ensure you get credit for your work.

Our Mission

In order to realize our vision, ORCID strives to enable transparent and trustworthy connections between researchers, their contributions, and their affiliations by providing a unique, persistent identifier for individuals to use as they engage in research, scholarship, and innovation activities.

We do this by providing three interrelated services:

The ORCID ID: a unique, persistent identifier free of charge to researchers

An **ORCID record** connected to the ORCID ID, and

A set of **Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)**, as well as the services and support of communities of practice that enable interoperability between an ORCID record and member organizations so researchers can choose to allow connection of their ID with their affiliations and contributions

Our Plans

The core of our strategic focus for 2022–2025 is to **build commitment to and engagement with** ORCID as an **essential element of the research experience**, both for researchers and members. We invite you to review [From Vision to Value: ORCID's 2022–2025 Strategic Plan](#). We hope it inspires our member organizations to engage with us as they plan their own work and activities.

Our Values

ORCID is an integral part of the wider digital infrastructure needed for researchers to share information on a global scale. We position

DOI

- Digital Object Identifier
- Foundation launched to develop system in 1998. First applications launched 2000
- Currently used by well over 5,000 assigners, e.g., publishers, science data centres, movie studios, etc.
- Approximately 257 million DOI names assigned to date

The DOI® System

ISO 26324

This is the web site of the International DOI Foundation (IDF), a not-for-profit [membership organization](#) that is the governance and management body for the [Federation of Registration Agencies](#) providing Digital Object Identifier (DOI) services and registration, and is the registration authority for the ISO standard (ISO 26324) for the DOI system. The DOI system provides a technical and social infrastructure for the registration and use of persistent Interoperable Identifiers, called DOIs, for use on digital networks.

Resolve a DOI Name

Type or paste a DOI name, e.g., 10.1000/xyz123, into the text box below. (Be sure to enter all of the characters before and after the slash. Do not include extra characters, or sentence punctuation marks.)

Clicking on a DOI link (try this one: <https://doi.org/10.1109/5.771073>) takes you to one or more current URLs or other services related to a single resource. If the URLs or services change over time, e.g., the resource moves, this same DOI will continue to resolve to the correct resources or services at their new locations.

Check the current status of the DOI system at doi.statuspage.io.

DRIVEN BY Enhance the value of your content.
Join the DOI Community.
[Watch a video, get the facts, and find out how.](#)

Updated May 13, 2021

contact@doi.org

DOI®, DOI.ORG®, and shortDOI® are trademarks of the International DOI Foundation.

[Privacy Policy](#) | [Accessibility](#)

1 results searching for ("Placing the Law next to the Social Dynamics") in Law Journal Library.

Sort by: Relevance

1.

(Re)Placing the Law next to the Social Dynamics: The Institutionalization of Sociology of Law in the Curricula and the Crossing of the Socio-Legal Research in the Law Graduation [article] **new**

Brazilian Journal of Empirical Legal Studies, Vol. 7, Issue 1 (April 2020), pp. 117-142

dos Santos, Thais Lemos

DOI: 10.19092/reed.v7i1.395

7 Braz. J. Empirical Legal Stud. 117 (2020)

Accessed 1

What is a Preprint?

- The version of an article before submission to a journal for peer review

What are the benefits of preprints?

Speed

- the manuscript is available within days

Authorship

- a public record that you published that research at that time

Review

- Other researchers can offer feedback

Research impact

- The research can be cited and built upon more quickly.

Preprints

- Publish fast
- Get a DOI (which means the article is citable)
- Upload new versions
- Submit to a journal later.

The Multidisciplinary Preprint Platform

Keyword/Title Author
Subject Categories Subjects Q

Preprints on COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2

- | | |
|------------------------------|---|
| All Subjects | Life Sciences |
| Arts & Humanities | Materials Science |
| Behavioral Sciences | Mathematics & Computer Science |
| Biology | Medicine & Pharmacology |
| Chemistry | Physical Sciences |
| Earth Sciences | Social Sciences |
| Engineering | |

<https://www.preprints.org/>

A preprint is a piece of research that has not yet been peer reviewed and published in a journal. In most cases, they can be considered final drafts or working papers. *Preprints* is a multidisciplinary preprint platform that makes scientific manuscripts from all fields of research immediately available. It is a free, not-for-profit service supported by the open access publisher MDPI.

Latest Articles

ARTICLE

A Novel Approach to the Holistic 3D Characterization of Weld Seams - Paving the Way for Deep Learning-Based Process Monitoring

Announced: 25 October 2021

ARTICLE

Carboxylation Capacity Can Limit Photosynthesis at Elevated CO₂ throughout Diurnal Cycles

Announced: 25 October 2021

ARTICLE

Determination of Avermectins Residues in Soybean, Bean and Maize Using a QuEChERS-based Method and Ultra-high-performance Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry

Announced: 25 October 2021

preprints.org > arts & humanities > history > doi: 10.20944/preprints202201.0420.v1

Preprint Article Version 1 Preserved in Portico This version is not peer-reviewed

A Framework for European Thought on Psychology, Education and Health Based on Foucault's The Order of Things

Version 1 : Received: 27 January 2022 / Approved: 27 January 2022 / Online: 27 January 2022 (12:32:18 CET)

How to cite: Nash, C. A Framework for European Thought on Psychology, Education and Health Based on Foucault's The Order of Things. *Preprints* 2022, 2022010420 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202201.0420.v1). [Copy](#)

Abstract

In European thought, the relationship among the fields of psychology, education, and health is both complex and obscured. Foucault's acclaimed work, *The Order of Things*, offers a framework to evaluate their interconnection by identifying three distinct periods of European thought since the 16th century with respect to the ordering of phenomena—Renaissance, Classical and Modern. Theoretically dense and often difficult to decipher, the book's categorization of language, value and being has been understandably underused, yet it provides deep insights into what have come to be known as psychology, education and health and remains invaluable in understanding the origin, limits and consequences of these fields. How Foucault's analysis can be interpreted concerning the development of these areas as to each of the three periods of European thought is investigated. An approach based on narrative research appraises the analysis offered in the book. The results, presented for the first time in table form, compare these three periods, demonstrating a continuing practical value to Foucault's insights. With the aid of the framework revealed by these tables, the boundaries and relationship of psychology, education and health become clear and their limitations—plus potential solutions to them—can be identified to mitigate

Citation

- Kim, K.; Lim, G.G. Developing A Contingency Model of Export Marketing Strategy on E-commerce for MSMEs. Preprints 2021, 2021100068

<https://preprints.apsanet.org/engage/apsa/public-dashboard>

Browse Categories

American Government and Politics 80	Comparative Politics 95	International Relations 51
Methodology 19	Political Science Education and the Profession 82	Political Theory 33
Politics of Gender 4	Politics of Sexuality 2	Public Administration 5
Public Law and Courts 4	Public Opinion and Voting Behavior 35	Public Policy 22
Race, Ethnicity and Politics 11		

Political Theory

Normative Political Science – How to Measure the Goodness of a Political System

WORKING PAPER William Kelleher

Abstract

As is well known, David Easton defines the political system as emerging from those social interactions undertaken in relation to the authoritative allocation of values for a society. This paper explains two normative services that Easton's definition can provide for political science; one is explanatory, the other evaluative. The explanatory service is to show both the distinctiveness of political science as a social science and to serve as a standard, or norm, by which to set the boundaries of the profession's subject matter. Secondly, Easton's theory of the political system as an input/output model can serve as a standard by which to assess the "goodness" of a political system, and for comparing the goodness of systems. Assessing such goodness is not a matter of moral approval or approbation, but more like the taxonomist assessing the goodness of a specimen, as to both its categorical fit and its health.

DOWNLOAD

Version History

Jul 28, 2021 Version 1

Metrics

4 1,675 Views
271 Content Downloads

License

The content is available under CC BY 4.0 License
[CreativeCommons.org](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

DOI

10.23274/apsa-2021-09wv

HC HUMANITIES COMMONS

Search [] [] Register Log In

News Feed
Members
Groups
Sites
CORE Repository
Help & Support
HC Organizations
About
Roadmap
Team Blog

Welcome to CORE: Open Access for the Humanities

A nonprofit, interdisciplinary, broad-ranging alternative to commercial networks

[Upload Your Work](#)

[Find Open Access Materials](#)

[The Library and Information Science Collection](#)

Recent Deposits

[Logical academic argumentation: Hybridization of competing epistemological and logical methodologies for doctoral research](#)
Original doctoral research requires a niche contribution to a boundless, colossal, and prodigious corpus of existing scholarship. The efficacy of...

[The Portrait of a Doctor](#)
This article begins with a brief dilation on the characteristics of a unified doctoral identity then transitions to a comprehensive...

[That way madness lies: Doctoral](#)

About CORE

[Frequently Asked Questions](#)
[Acknowledgments](#)

Why CORE?

Not just articles and monographs: Upload your course materials, white papers, conference papers, code, digital projects—these can have an impact too!

Community notifications: Send instant notifications about the work you've shared to members of your *Humanities Commons* groups.

Citation and attribution: All items uploaded to CORE get a DOI, or digital object identifier that serves as a

<https://hcommons.org/core/>

News Feed

Members

Groups

Sites

CORE Repository

Help & Support

HC Organizations

About

Roadmap

Team Blog

Why should I deposit my work with *CORE*?

PRESERVATION Depositing your work with a repository ensures that it is archived and attributed to you and makes it quickly and widely available to others.

ACCESS AND PRIVACY Uploading scholarship to *CORE* makes it quickly and widely available to others—without requiring them to register for *Humanities Commons* or provide us with any personal information.

ATTRIBUTION Works deposited with *CORE* are automatically given a permanent identifier called a DOI. DOIs provide persistent, citable metadata for scholarly and creative works, including gray literature such as blog posts, syllabi, data sets, presentations, and video and audio files.

DISCOVERABILITY Materials uploaded to *CORE* are indexed by Google, Google Scholar, SHARE, Altmetric, and BASE-OA, which fuels open-access initiatives such as the OA Button and OA DOI. Since you can notify the members of any of

- News Feed
- Members
- Groups
- Sites
- CORE Repository
- Help & Support
- HC Organizations
- About
- Roadmap
- Team Blog

Biopolitics of COVID-19: Capitalist Continuities and Democratic Openings

Author(s): [Karsten Schubert \(see profile\)](#)

Date: 2022

Group(s): [Frankfurt School Critical Theory](#), [Global & Transnational Studies](#), [Political Philosophy & Theory](#), [Queer and Trans German Studies](#), [Queer Theory Group](#)

Subject(s): [Political philosophy](#), [Political theory](#), [Queer theory](#), [Michel Foucault](#), [Biopolitics](#)

Item Type: [Article](#)

Tag(s): [covid-19](#), [pandemic](#), [Democracy](#)

Permanent URL: <https://doi.org/10.17613/e2xw-wj60>

Abstract: "Biopolitics" has become a popular concept for interpreting the COVID-19 pandemic, yet the term is often used vaguely, as a buzzword, and therefore loses its specificity and

Research
Skills 2

Literature
Search

- Researchgate and Academia
- Cambridge University Library

Researchgate and Academia

- Researchgate
- 20m scholars
- A mashup of Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn (NY Times)
- Academia
- 71m scholars

<https://www.academia.edu/>

Founded in 2008 by physicians [Dr. Jjad Madisch](#) and [Dr. Sören Hofmayer](#), and computer scientist [Horst Fickenscher](#), ResearchGate has more than 20 million members today. We strive to help them make progress happen faster.

Here's how it works

Share your publications, access millions more, and publish your data.

Connect and collaborate with colleagues, peers, co-authors, and specialists.

Get stats and find out who's been reading and citing your work.

Ask questions, get answers, and solve research problems.

Find the right job using our research-focused job board.

Share updates about your current project, and keep up with the latest research.

R^G Home Questions Jobs Search for researchers, publications, and more [Add new](#)

Christine Luk
i1 5.75 · PhD

[Follow](#)

Overview Research Experience Scores

About Christine

Skills and expertise

Hong Kong Modern China History ... Biology History ... Science

Stats overview

605 Reads	
2	

Current affiliation

The University of Hong Kong

Location
Hong Kong, Hong Kong

Department
Hong Kong Institute for the Humanities and Social Sciences

Position
PostDoc Position

Network

Stats overview

605 Reads <small>📄</small>	9 Citations <small>📄</small>
2 Recommendations <small>👍</small>	11.3 Total Research Interest <small>📄</small>

Research

Research overview

10 Research items	0 Projects	0 Questions	0 Answers
----------------------	---------------	----------------	--------------

[View all](#) 📄

Featured research

Building Biophysics in Mid-Century China: The University of Science and Technology of China

Article Full text available January 2015 Journal of the History of Biology

Hong Kong Institute for the Humanities and Social Sciences

Position
PostDoc Position

Network

Following (14) [View all](#) 📄

- Nicolas Rasmussen**
·iI 28.94 · UNSW Sydney [Follow](#)
- Danian Hu**
·iI 14 · City College of N... [Follow](#)
- Erik Baark**
·iI 24.74 · The Hong Ko... [Follow](#)

Followers (12) [View all](#) 📄

- Zongan Wang**
·iI 22.2 · Beijing Genomi... [Follow](#)
- Mingyang Li**
Chinese Academy of Sci... [Follow](#)
- Jos Estevez**
The University of Hong ... [Follow](#)

Cambridge University Library

- One of the world's major research libraries
- 9m items
- 15m items across all 116 libraries in the university
- British Library – 170m
- US Library of Congress – 170m
- Beijing + Shanghai 94m

<https://www.lib.cam.ac.uk/>

iDiscover

Cambridge Libraries Collections Articles and online resources Search everything

plato

All Libraries

Advanced Search
Browse

Sign in to renew or request items Login to iDiscover DISMISS

0 selected PAGE 1 12,487 Results

- JOURNAL**

Plato : the internet journal of the International Plato Society.

International Plato Society.
Began with [Plato 1](#) (2001). [Place of publication not identified] : International Plato Society

[Online access](#) >
- BOOK**

The mind of Plato / by A.E. Taylor.

A. E. Taylor (Alfred Edward), 1869-1945.
1st American ed. Ann Arbor, Mich. : University of Michigan Press, 1960.

Available at Magdalene College Library Main Library (2.F.47) >
- BOOK**

Introducing Plato / Dave Robinson and Judy Groves.

Dave. Robinson ; Judy Groves
Trumpington : Icon, 2000.

Refine my results

Sort by Relevance

Availability

Available in the Library (9,103)

Full Text Online (3,709)

Resource Type

Books (12,188)

Theses (203)

Other (75)

Scores (18)

Audio Visual (14)

Show More

Date

From 1000

To 2022

Refine

BOOK
The Cambridge companion to Plato / edited by Richard Kraut.

Richard Kraut, 1944- editor.
 Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 1992. ©1992

!!! Available at Philosophy (Casimir Lewy Library) Main Library (A.12 PLA Cam) and other locations >

≡ Chapters of this book (17) >

- TOP
- SEND TO
- GET IT
- DETAILS
- LINKS

Send to

[EXPORT TO EXCEL](#)
[EXPORT BIBTEX](#)
[RIS \(ENDNOTE/ ZOTERO\)](#)
[CITATION](#)
[PERMALINK](#)
[PRINT](#)
[E-MAIL](#)

Get it

[Sign-in for more options](#) [Login to iDiscover](#)

REQUEST OPTIONS:

Year	Volume	Description
Christ's College Library > Floor 1 >	B395.C3 1992	from:Copy 1 until:Copy 2
Churchill College Library > Bracken Library >	184.1	
Clare College (Forbes Mellon Library) > Main Library >	184 PLA-K	
Classical Faculty Library > Main Library >	F 4.1 52	
Corpus Christi College > Taylor Library >	K.2.PLA	

BOOK
The Cambridge companion to Plato / edited by Richard Kraut.

Richard Kraut, 1944- editor.
Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 1992. ©1992

!!! Available at Philosophy (Casimir Lewy Library) Main Library (A.12 PLA Cam) and other locations >
Chapters of this book (17) >

- TOP
- SEND TO
- GET IT
- DETAILS
- LINKS

Send to

EXPORT TO EXCEL EXPORT BIBTEX RIS (ENDNOTE/ZOTERO) CITATION PERMALINK PRINT E-MAIL

MLA (7th edition)
APA (6th edition)
Chicago/Turabian (16th edition)
MLA (8th edition)
Harvard Reference format (7th edition)

Kraut, R. (1992). *The Cambridge companion to Plato* (Cambridge companions to philosophy).

COPY THE CITATION TO CLIPBOARD

Remember to check citations for accuracy before including them in your work

Get it

Sign-in for more options Login to iDiscover

REQUEST OPTIONS:

Year All Volume All Description All

Darwin Correspondence Project

Home About Darwin The letters Commentary People Learning Resources About us

Search over 15000 letters and articles...

Search

advanced search >

Search: contains "evolution"

Letters, people & references [933] Articles [163]

Search:

evolution in keywords

933 items

Sorted by: relevance

Go!

Page: 1 2 3 4 5 ... Next

From Gaston de Saporta 10 April 1881

Sends GdeS and A. F. Marion, *L'évolution du règne végétal. Les cryptogames* [1881].

Author: Louis Charles Joseph Gaston (Gaston) de Saporta, comte de Saporta
Addressee: Charles Robert Darwin
Date: 10 Apr 1881
Classmark: DAR 177: 38
Letter no: DCP-LETT-13111

Matches: 12 hits

- ... Sends GdeS and A. F. Marion, *L'évolution du règne végétal. Les cryptogames* [1881]. ...
- ... and Marion, Antoine-Fortuné. 1881. *L'évolution du règne végétal. Les cryptogames*. Paris: ...

REFINE YOUR SEARCH

Document type

letter (691)
bibliography (150)
people (92)

Author

MORE +

Darwin, C. R. (299)
Hooker, J. D. (24)
Ramanes, G. J. (18)
Haeckel, Ernst (14)
Krause, Ernst (12)

Addressee

MORE +

Darwin, C. R. (380)
Hooker, J. D. (25)
Ramanes, G. J. (21)
Krause, Ernst (15)
Lyll, Charles (15)

Correspondent

MORE +

Darwin, C. R. (679)
Hooker, J. D. (49)
Ramanes, G. J. (39)
Krause, Ernst (27)
Huxley, T. H. (23)

Date

1832 (1)

Electronic Collections: journals and databases

Over 130,000 ejournal titles and 400 databases are available off-campus. Find your essential guide to Cambridge University Libraries' services and support for online resources on our [E-resources pages](#).

Discover the latest on [ebooks & ejournals](#), including:

- [Browzine](#) - a new way to browse scholarly journals by title and subject area, and to create your own journal and article library.
- an [iDiscover widget](#) to help you search for articles or journals online
- [highlights of new e-resources](#) available for the academic year 2020/21.

Visit [How to access e-resources](#) to learn all you need to know about accessing and using eresources easily and safely including:

- a [Raven LibGuide](#) for help and support on using Raven to authenticate for access to e-resources from off campus.
- a new browser extension, [LibKey Nomad](#), which automatically connects University members to online resources subscribed by Cambridge University Libraries.
- help on navigating authentication procedures on different platforms.
- full information on terms and conditions for use of e-resources.

You can also find free open access research outputs on the institutional research repositories round the world. These should appear in a Google search, but you can also search Cambridge's institutional repository, [Apollo](#).

A list of additional e-resources made freely available during the pandemic through the generosity of publishers can be accessed [through this page](#).

New electronic resources for 2021

A new set of electronic resources is available for 2021 thanks to funding from the University of Cambridge to support continued teaching and learning throughout the Covid-19 pandemic. We have added the resources to our vast online library, so that you can keep studying, teaching and researching, wherever you are this term. The links below will take you to the Electronic Collections Management blog, where you can learn more about these resources and how to access them.

[Leading scholarly content to support all subject areas](#)

Help

All A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z #

22 Databases found for F [Clear Filters/Browse All Databases](#)

F

- [Faber Poetry Library, The](#) ⓘ ⓘ
- [Fabula](#) ⓘ ⓘ
- [Fabula / Colloques en ligne](#) ⓘ ⓘ
- [Factiva](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ
Link temporarily not working. Please contact info@lib.cam.ac.uk for help.
[less](#)
- [Factiva](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ
Factiva is a database of over 8,000 business and news publications, most in full text. Sources are in 22 languages, date back as far as 1969, and include trade journals, newswires (Dow Jones, Reuters, and others), media programs, and company and stock reports. Find information on over 22,000 public and private companies including description, history, current stock quote, financial data, competitors, and the latest news on business activities. Search publications by title, industry, geographic locations, type, and language.
- [FAME](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ
- [FIAP International Index to Film Periodicals Database](#) ⓘ ⓘ
- [Fihrist: Islamic Manuscripts Catalogue Online](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ
- [Film Index International](#) ⓘ ⓘ
- [Financial Times](#) ⓘ ⓘ
- [Financial Times FT Historical Archive, 1888-2016](#) ⓘ ⓘ
- [First World War](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ
- [FirstSearch](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ

Chat with us

Have a question about eJournals and eResources? Chat with us using our new LibChat service!

Currently, the chat is live Monday to Friday 1000-1200 and 1400-1600.

If you want to get in touch with us outside these hours, please email ejournals@lib.cam.ac.uk

Live Chat available 10am-12pm and 2pm-4pm daily

Name (blank=anonymous)

Your Question*

Start Chat

Popular Databases

The most frequently-used databases

- [British Humanities Index](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ Popular ⓘ
- [ClinicalKey Student](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ Popular ⓘ
[more...](#)
- [JSTOR](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ Popular ⓘ
- [Scopus](#) ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ ⓘ

Help

D | DOW JONES PROFESSIONAL SOLUTIONS ▾ MEDIA BRANDS ▾ PRESS ROOM ABOUT CAREERS 🔍 PRODUCT LOG IN ▾ **CONTACT**

Research, Strategy & Competitive Intelligence

Power strategic decisions, uncover competitive advantage and deliver actionable intelligence with global news, data and insights.

[Learn More →](#)

Advanced Analytics & Data Mining

Generate deeper insights, improve sentiment analysis, uncover hidden relationships, accurately forecast and enrich data visualizations with news data derived from advanced analytics models.

[Learn More →](#)

Media Monitoring & Corporate Communications

Keep track of your brand's reputation and stay ahead of potential issues by leveraging a database of content from 200 countries in 28 languages, comprehensive monitoring tools and curation solutions.

[Learn More →](#)

Competitive Intelligence

Gather market intelligence, monitor competitors and provide strategic guidance with trusted world news, detailed company and executive data and multi-channel delivery.

[Learn More →](#)

Sales Funnel & Business Development

Empower your global sales and business development teams to grow the pipeline, target companies and connect with clients by using news from more than 33,000 global sources and a database of millions of corporate profiles.

[Learn More →](#)

Application Development

Innovate and differentiate with premium news integrated into application interfaces, such as company intranet portals or customer engagement apps.

[Learn More →](#)

RECOMMENDED

News Data Fuels Economic Development and Investor Identification

Hi there 🤖 Anything I can help you with today?

Content & Workflow Integration Customer Engagement & Marketing

<https://www.dowjones.com/professional/factiva/>

BrowZine Library My Bookshelf My Articles

Access Provided By University of Cambridge

Press F11 to exit full screen

ACCESS PROVIDED BY UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE

FIND JOURNAL BY TITLE, SUBJECT, OR ISSN

BROWSE SUBJECTS

- Arts and Humanities
- Biological Sciences
- Biomedical and Health Sciences
- Business and Economics
- Earth and Environmental Sciences
- Engineering and Technology
- History
- Law and Legal Studies
- Mathematics and Statistics
- Philosophy and Religion
- Physics, Chemistry and Astronomy

The main content area displays a grid of journal covers. Visible titles include Nature Medicine, Cell, Journal of Materials Chemistry, C&EN, The Digital Scholar, ASIANART NEWS, MOCHTAR APIN, postmedieval, cellular microbiology, Journal, Biophysical Journal, and Developmental Biology. The covers feature various scientific and artistic illustrations.

Change Subject

Philosophy and Religion

CATEGORIES

All Journals >

Philosophy

Religion

SORT A-Z / JOURNAL RANK

グローバル・コン
サレン

ACM
Transactions
on

Acta Analytica

Acta Baltica
Historiae et
Philosophiae

Acta Bioethica

Acta
Universitatis
Carolinae:

Acta
Universitatis
Carolinae

Addin

AI and Ethics

AJS Review

Al-Ahwal:
Jurnal Hukum
Keluarga Islam

Al-Abab

Al-A'raf: Jurnal
Pemikiran
Islam dan

Al-Athfal:
Jurnal
Pendidikan

Algemeen
Nederlands
Tijdschrift voor

Al-Izzah

Al-Jami'ah:
Journal of
Islamic Studies

Alpha: Revista
de Artes Letras
y Filosofia

Al-Qantara:
Revista de
Estudios

Al-Tadzkiyyah:
Jurnal
Pendidikan

Al-Tahrir

American
Jewish
History

American
Library
Studies

American
Jewish
History

< Back to Journals

SJR: Unranked

AI and Ethics

ADD TO MY BOOKSHELF

NEW ARTICLES

Articles in Press

JOURNAL ISSUES

- 2021 > Vol 1 Issue 4 >
- See All [See All](#)
- Vol 1 Issue 3
- Vol 1 Issue 2
- Vol 1 Issue 1

BROWSE RELATED SUBJECTS

- Artificial Intelligence/Robotics
- Business Ethics and Public Responsibility
- Ethics and Professional Responsibility
- Ethics/Bioethics
- Medical Ethics

2021 Vol. 1 Issue 4

'The names have changed, but the game's the same': artificial intelligence and racial policy in the USA

pp. 389-394 - Wallace, R.

Like the Operations Research models used to justify the ethnic cleansing of minority voting blocs in 1970's New York City, AI 'risk assessment' systems for individuals will be used to reinforce longstanding power relations between ethnic groups within the USA. From the perspective of African-Americans and their abolitionist allies, the central problem with AI risk assessment does not involve 'corrective' stabilization of an inadvertently unstable system. On the contrary, ...

Facebook's ethical failures are not accidental; they are part of the business model

pp. 395-403 - Lauer, David

Philosophical foundations for digital ethics and AI Ethics: a dignitarian approach

pp. 405-423 - Hanna, Robert; Kazim, Emre

is a burgeoning and relatively new field that has emerged in response to growing concerns about the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on human individuals and their social institutions. In turn, AI ethics is a part of the broader field of digital ethics, which addresses similar concerns generated by the development and deployment of new digital technologies. Here, we tackle the important worry that digital ethics in general, and AI ethics in particular, lack adequate philosoph...

Sensitivity of neural networks to corruption of image classification

pp. 425-434 - Kaplan, Shimon; Handelman, Doron; Handelman, Amir

Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are extensively used today in many fields. In the field of medicine, AI-systems are especially used for the segmentation and classification of medical images. As reliance on such AI-systems increases, it is important to verify that these systems are dependable and not sensitive to bias or other types of errors that may severely affect users and patients. This work investigates the sensitivity of the performance of AI-systems to labeling errors. ...

Research Skills 3

- The Publishing Process
- From Editing to Publication

Proofreading and Editing

- Proofreading
 - Language
- Editing
 - Everything from style to structure and format

Reviewer Problems

The reviewer has
bad English

The reviewer
requests changes
in the English!

Publishing your Article

Target a Journal

Find the most suitable one
Be realistic

Check the journal conditions

Scope
Article length
Submission guidelines

- Conventions
- Typography
- Word count

Four Types of Journals and Platforms

Traditional

Open Access

Free for all, not peer-reviewed

Predatory

<https://www.researchgate.net/>
<https://www.academia.edu/>

Traditional

- Readers can access articles
- By subscription (paid by a library)
 - Low/no submission fee paid by Author
- By Open Access
 - The Author pays a fee of up to around \$3,000 (when article is accepted)
- Examples
 - Springer
 - Elsevier

Elsevier publishes 500,000 articles a year in 2,500 journals.

Open Access

- By Open Access
- The reader can access the journal for free
- The Author pays an APC of up to around \$3,000 (when article is accepted)

- Good Open Access journals
- Double blind, peer review

- Example: PLOS (Public Library of Science)

Free Platforms

Researchgate

- 11 million users

Academia

- 42/71/142 million users

Premium versions -
subscription

Who Publishes on Researchgate / Academia?

Young academics

Independent researchers

People who want to get the message out fast

Established researchers

- Some universities take this into account regarding promotion

Some Professors

- The Professor of Linguistics, Prague (many of his papers)

Predatory Journals

- Poor Quality
- No / poor peer group review
- Don't care about English standard
- No impact
- Submission charge

- These journals prey upon authors...

'Academic' publishers and titles identified as predatory, 2011-16

Selecting a Journal

- Match
 - Your field
 - Your sub-field
 - Your article – what it is about
- With
 - Target journals

Ancient Philosophy Journal Experiences and Time Frames, June 2020 Update

June 22, 2020

Last September, I highlighted what recent public surveys submitted to the [APA Journal Surveys](#) project indicated about the editorial experience at journals that specialize in ancient philosophy and the history of philosophy. I'm writing to provide another update based on recent surveys (though things have not changed too much). The journals that get the best ratings for editorial experience are also the quickest. The [British Journal for the History of Philosophy](#) and the [Journal of the History of Philosophy](#) continue to lead the way in editor experience scores. The [APA journal surveys site](#) asks respondents to rate the overall editorial experience from 1-5 and these two are the only ones with ratings in the 4.5-5 range, with [BJHP](#) averaging 4.6 and [JHP](#) averaging 4.5. They are also among the quickest (1.5 months for [JHP](#) and 2.9 for [BJHP](#)) and among the most transparent about their editorial practices.

The next three journals with good editorial experience scores are the [Classical Quarterly](#), the [History of Philosophy Quarterly](#), and [Phronesis](#). They all have editorial experience scores around 4 (4.1 for [CQ](#), and 3.9 for [HPQ](#) and [Phronesis](#)). [Phronesis](#) has the quickest turnaround time (1.9 months), with [CQ](#) averaging 3.5 months and [HPQ](#) 5.6 months.

[Ancient Philosophy](#) has middling editorial experience ratings (3.4/5) and averages 4.8 months to respond, while [Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie](#) (2.4/5) and [Oxford Studies in Ancient Philosophy](#) (2.2/5) receive the lowest editorial experience ratings. They also have fairly long wait times (average of 6.1 months for [Archiv](#) and 8.8 months for [OSAP](#)). However, [Victor Caston](#), editor of [OSAP](#), informed me last year that times to decision for manuscripts submitted in 2019 were significantly lower than in 2018. He expected the overall average decision time for 2019 manuscripts to be within or lower than [OSAP's](#) target range of 4 to 6 months.

There are no recent surveys available for [Apeiron: A Journal for Ancient Philosophy and Science](#), but [Luis Salas](#), Associate Editor at [Apeiron](#), shared their internal statistics last year, showing averaged decision times of 3 months. Salas noted that 345 of the manuscripts (about 75% of the total) received a decision in less than 3 months and about

ABOUT

A site featuring information and resources for teaching and scholarship in ancient philosophy, run by Caleb Cohoe, Professor of Philosophy at MSU Denver.

τοῦ βλῆγου δ' ἔονται ξυνοῦ,
ζῶουσι οἱ πολλοὶ ὡς ἴδιην
ἔχοντες φρόνησιν.

SEARCH

RECENT COMMENTS

Interview with Thornton Lockwood

(Quinnipiac), Editor of Polis –

Eudoxa on Interview with Anna

Marmodoro (Durham and Oxford),

editor of Ancient Philosophy Today

OSAP to Change Editorial Practices:

Announcements Rachana Kamtekar as

<https://endoxa.blog/2020/06/22/ancient-philosophy-journal-experiences-and-time-frames-june-2020-update/>

Platforms and Indexers

Platforms

- Springer
- Elsevier
- Taylor and Francis
- PLOS
- ArXiv
- Researchgate
- Academia

Indexers

- Scopus (Elsevier)
- SCI (9,000 journals)
- SSCI (3,400 journals)
- Pubmed (30m citations and abstracts) (Ebscohost)
- Ulrichsweb (420,000 journals)
- DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) (5.5m articles)

<https://clarivate.com/webofsciencegroup/solutions/webofscience-ssci/>

<https://libanswers.lib.xjtlu.edu.cn/faq/220443>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/about/>

<https://www.ebsco.com/products/research-databases/academic-search>

[https://knowledge.exlibrisgroup.com/Ulrich's/Product_Documentation/Frequently_Asked_Questions_\(FAQs\)/Ulrichsweb%3A_General_FAQ](https://knowledge.exlibrisgroup.com/Ulrich's/Product_Documentation/Frequently_Asked_Questions_(FAQs)/Ulrichsweb%3A_General_FAQ)

<https://doaj.org/>

Publishing Output

- Some scientists publish 70+ papers per year
- How?
 - Co-authorship
 - Overlapping content
 - Many research notes
- Why?
 - Publish or perish, university requirements
- Does it help?
 - Maybe
 - Although there is nothing better than
 - Quality
 - Single / few authors

<https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2018/09/some-scientists-publish-more-70-papers-year-here-s-how-and-why-they-do-it>

The Publishing Process

- Editing
 - English, style, cohesion/coherence, citations, references, formatting
- Submission Checklist
 - Author information
 - Author declaration – original work, no competing interests
- Submit
- Pay submission fee
- Editor's reply
 - Accept for review
 - reject
- Peer review
- Accept / accept with changes / reject

How much does it cost?

Journal / platform	Peer reviewed	Fees	Revenue model
Traditional (Elsevier)	Yes	\$175 (submission fee) up to \$3,000 (Article Processing Charge)	Library subscriptions Open Access
Open Access (PLOS)	Yes	up to \$3,000 (APC)	Article Processing Charge (APC)
ResearchGate	No	Free	Premium subscriptions

Research
Skills 4

Publishing

- Peer Review

Peer Review Process

WILEY

30011

Double Blind Review Process

The reviewer(s) unknown to the author

The author unknown to the reviewer(s)

Peer review

The article is reviewed by an expert in your field

The Peer Review Process

<http://sitn.hms.harvard.edu/flash/2015/as-good-as-it-gets-peer-review-and-its-discontents/>

How long
does it take?

6 – 12 months+

The editor can
send the article
back for revisions

A Typical Review Form (1)

(1) Title	Adequate and important?		Yes	√	No
(1) Abstract	Adequate		Needs amendments		Unacceptable
(1) Introduction	Adequate		Needs amendments		Unacceptable
(1) Review of literature	Adequate		Needs amendments		Unacceptable
(1) Methodology	Adequate		Needs amendments		Unacceptable
(1) Results and discussion	Adequate		Needs amendments		Unacceptable
(1) Conclusion	Adequate		Needs amendments		Unacceptable
(1) References / bibliography	Adequate		Needs amendments		Unacceptable
(1) Language	Adequate		Needs improvement		Unacceptable
(1) Overall structure	Adequate		Needs improvement		Unacceptable
(1) Originality	Adequate		Needs Improvement		Unacceptable

A Typical Review Form (2)

Decision	
Manuscript is accepted in the present form	Manuscript is accepted with minor changes
Manuscript is accepted with major changes	Manuscript is rejected
Final comments and recommendations (if any):	

Reviewers' Comments

- The reviewers may comment on
 - The academic content
 - The consistency and connection of ideas through the text
 - Abstract, introduction, body, conclusions
 - Consistent labelling of tables and figures
 - Citations and references
 - The standard of English

Reviewers' Comments – Example 1

- **REVIEW 1**

- **English grammatical errors** are throughout the manuscript in numerous places. Please use some **grammar check software** to fix these errors.
- Page **3**: Last paragraph:
- Please provide **the specific objectives of the study** and highlight how this paper is **different** from previous relevant studies in the literature (What new are you contributing, how are you contributing, what experimental methods you are using to present these findings etc.)

Reviewers' Comments – Example 2

- **Reviewer #2:** In this manuscript, the authors reported that a simple method employing sol-gel coating of nanoparticles with titania followed by controlled silver diffusion was developed and applied to the synthesis of Ag-doped hollow TiO₂ spheres. The Ag-TiO₂ hollow nanostructures with a different content of Ag embedded into TiO₂ were prepared using the developed method simply by a change of annealing time in the last step of fabrication. The synthesized nanostructures exhibit significant absorption in the UV-vis range.
- Although the approach is interesting, the present paper contains several weak points, originating **from the fact that the lack of novelty and poor broader impact (e.g., readership)**. The authors have not disclosed new results; especially in the topic of Ag-TiO₂ hollow nanostructures. **There are many similar literature and journals have been reported over the past 10 years.** The authors should further **emphasize on** their research novelty compared to **other's** work for synthesising Ag-doped hollow TiO₂ spheres via sol-gel technique followed by controlled silver diffusion. The authors should conduct more characterization analyses including HRTEM, XRD, pL, Raman, EIS, etc as well as photocatalysis performance evaluation **test** to confirm that the synthesized nanostructures exhibit significant absorption in the UV-vis range. Furthermore, **carefully English correction** is necessary for the whole manuscript. In my opinion, the manuscript contains few experimental results is at a moderate scientific level, rendering this in its present form inappropriate for publication in Applied Surface Science.

Reviewers' Comments – Example 3 (my review)

The subject matter and argument are well presented.

Perhaps the parts of the article could be **rebalanced** a little. The introduction accounts for more than 10% of the total and is perhaps a little too long. Since the analysis is very good, it would not hurt to add some more.

Further, **it is not completely clear where the concluding remarks begin**. Indeed, the word **“conclusions” does not occur in the text**. This needs to be clearly indicated.

The English needs to be improved as follows:

Omission of the article *a*, and *the* (especially in sentence initial position).

A small number of spelling errors.

Incorrect use of “so” and “while” in initial sentence position.

Watch out for the position of the full stop at the end of a sentence with a citation: this is not correct in all instances.

Where to Publish?

Use a Journal
Finder

Springer
Journal
Suggester

Sage Journal
Selector

<https://journalsuggester.springer.com/>

<https://philosophy.berkeley.edu/file/642/BLC2011Abstracts.pdf>

SPRINGER NATURE
Journal suggester

Personalized recommendation

Our journal matching technology finds relevant journals based on your manuscript details

Over 2,500 journals

Search all Springer and BMC journals to find the most suitable journal for your manuscript

Author choice

Easily compare relevant journals to find the best place for publication

Enter your manuscript details to see a list of journals most suitable for your research.

Manuscript title

Manuscript text

This paper addresses a puzzle with regard to the question of Kant's understanding of the relationship between the methods of mathematics and metaphysics. In the preface to the Critique of Pure Reason, Kant indicates that metaphysics' success depends on its adopting the method of the mathematicians; in a later section of the first Critique, Kant explicitly warns against doing so. I'll argue that we should in fact understand Kant's explicit warnings as qualified, and view Kant as endorsing a unified methodology for both mathematics and metaphysics. This uniformity of methodology, I'll suggest, is determined with regard to shared features within the procedures through which mathematical and metaphysical concepts are acquired

Subject area

[+ Refine your recommendations](#)

<p>Synthese</p> <p>			
<p>Sophia</p> <p>			
<p>Philosophia</p> <p>			
<p>International Journal for Philosophy of Religion</p> <p>			
<p>Continental Philosophy Review</p> <p>			

AUTHOR SERVICES
Supporting Taylor & Francis authors

Home > How to publish your research > Choosing a journal > Taylor & Francis Journal Suggester

Journal Suggester

BETA

Helping you find the best home for your research article

There are two easy steps

Step 1: Paste in the full abstract of your article.
The suggestions will be more accurate if you use a full abstract containing relevant keywords.

Step 2: Click on 'Reveal suggested journals' to see a short description of the journal and some citation and speed metrics.

This paper addresses a puzzle with regard to the question of Kant's understanding of the relationship between the methods of mathematics and metaphysics. In the preface to the Critique of Pure Reason, Kant indicates that metaphysics' success depends on its adopting the method of the mathematicians; in a later section of the first Critique, Kant explicitly warns against doing so. I'll argue that we should in fact understand Kant's explicit warnings as qualified, and view Kant as endorsing a unified methodology for both mathematics and metaphysics. This uniformity of methodology, I'll suggest, is determined with regard to shared features within the procedures through which mathematical and metaphysical concepts are acquired.

Feedback

<https://www.edanz.com/journal-selector/publisher/sage>

Suggested Journals

Show full open access journals only

Definitions
[Full open access](#) [Open Select](#)

British Journal for the History of Philosophy

About Metrics

Publishes research on the history of philosophy from the ancient world to the 20th century, focusing on philosophical argumentation and historical development.

Learn more and submit

or visit the [cost finder](#) to calculate the article publishing charge

South African Journal of Philosophy

About Metrics

Publishing in all areas of African philosophy, including epistemology, communitarianism, human capital flight, and personhood.

Learn more and submit

or visit the [cost finder](#) to calculate the article publishing charge

Educational Philosophy and Theory

About Metrics

Educational Philosophy and Theory publishes articles on all aspects of educational

Australasian Journal of Philosophy

About Metrics

The Australasian Journal of Philosophy is one of the world's leading philosophy journals covering topics like general philo-

Contact us

Feedback

What if the
article is
rejected?

- The article could be rejected because of
 - Poor English
 - Poor academic quality
 - Content
 - Style / argumentation
 - Plagiarism

Poland - Case Study

- A scientific article from Poland
- The article was sent back – Plagiarism
- Question to Mark:
 - “Can you change the language?”
- Answer:
 - “Very difficult, you need to write fresh text”
- The result was a mess
- Back to the drawing board!

The Journal

Energies

In Science Citation Index

Impact factor 2.702

Publisher – MDPI (over
275 journals)

Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute

<https://www.mdpi.com/about>

APC 2200 USD

Search for Articles:

Title / Keyword

Author / Affiliation

Energies

All Article Types

Search

Advanced

Journals / Energies

Submit to Energies

Review for Energies

Share

Journal Menu

- Energies Home
- Aims & Scope
- Editorial Board
- Reviewer Board
- Topics Board
- Instructions for Authors
- Special Issues
- Sections & Collections
- Article Processing Charge
- Indexing & Archiving
- Editor's Choice Articles
- Most Cited & Viewed
- Journal Statistics
- Journal History
- Journal Awards
- Society Collaborations
- Editorial Office

Transitioning 74 Metropolitan Areas to 100% Clean, Renewable Energy

Energies

Energies (ISSN 1996-1073, CODEN: ENERGA) is a peer-reviewed open access journal of related scientific research, technology development, engineering, and the studies in policy and management and is published semi-monthly online by MDPI. The European Biomass Industry Association (EUBIA), Polish Society of Applied Electromagnetics (PTZE), Association of European Renewable Energy Research Centres (EUREC), and Institute for Chemical Processing of Coal (ICHPW) are affiliated with Energies and their members receive a discount on the article processing charges.

- **Open Access** —free for readers, with article processing charges (APC) paid by authors or their institutions.
- **High Visibility**: indexed by the Science Citation Index Expanded (Web of Science), EI Compendex, Scopus and other databases.
- **CiteScore** (2019 Scopus data): 3.8; ranked 19/101 (Q2) in "Control and Optimization", 62/216 (Q2) in "Energy Engineering and Power Technology", 208/670 (Q2) in "Electrical and Electronic Engineering", 33/98 (Q2) in "Fuel Technology", 9/23 (Q2) in "Energy (miscellaneous)", and 72/179

IMPACT FACTOR 2.702

E-Mail Alert

Add your e-mail address to receive forthcoming issues of this journal.

Enter Your E-Mail Address...

Subscribe

News

26 October 2020

Meet us at the China Materials Conference and Exhibition 2020, Qingdao, Shandong, China, November 19–21, 2020

11 September 2020

Meet us at the 4th Micro-Nano Optics Technology and Application Exchange Conference (MOTA2020), Chengdu, China, 28–29 September 2020

Energies

indexed by the Science Citation Index Expanded (Web of Science), Ei Compendex, Scopus and other databases.

CiteScore (2019 Scopus data): **3.8**

Rapid Publication

peer-reviewed and a first decision provided to authors approximately 15.9 days after submission

acceptance to publication is undertaken in 3.8 days

Poland – One Solution

01

Look at the material

02

Look at new material

03

Somehow create 1-2
new articles

A large orange semi-circle is positioned on the left side of the slide, partially overlapping the text.

Research
Skills 5

References

- Building your References

How many references?

- Short technical article
- Long humanities / social science article
- About 20
- 50 - 70

The Ideal Number of References

- Predicting Citations to Journal Articles:
The Ideal Number of References
- Michael J. Lovaglia
- The American Sociologist
- Vol. 22, No. 1 (Spring, 1991), pp. 49-64 (16
pages)
- Published By: Springer

Large numbers of references

The increasing number of references in scientific journal articles suggests **editors may prefer articles with many references**. Articles in first position in a journal issue are found to have more references. Researchers also may prefer articles with many references.

Two hypotheses are proposed to explain this preference

Large numbers of references

Two hypotheses are proposed to explain this preference:

1) If references represent the adequacy of review of relevant literature (an explanation "internal" to science), then **the number of references per page will affect citations.**

Large numbers of references

2) If references directly influence readers' judgment of quality (an explanation "external" to science), then **the total number of references will affect citations.**

- Analysis of articles in sociology supports hypothesis two.
- References may affect citations to an article; references per page do not.
- **The ideal number of references in a sociology article is estimated at sixty-six.**

Finding References

- Look at the reference list at the end of good articles

G. E. R. Lloyd, *Principles and Practices in Ancient Greek and Chinese Science*, Aldershot/Burlington: Ashgate, 2006, xvi+302 pp.

In: [East Asian Science, Technology, and Medicine](#)

Author: [Lisa Raphals](#)

[View More +](#)

Online Publication Date: 25 Jun 2015

 Free access

[Download PDF](#)

[Download Citation](#)

[Get Permissions](#)

[Feedback](#)

< PREVIOUS ARTICLE

NEXT ARTICLE >

FREE

On the very possibility of mutual intelligibility

G. E. R. LLOYD
University of Cambridge

Abstract Full Text PDF EPUB MOBI

SECTIONS

- Abstract
- References
- Notes

Abstract

This paper acknowledges that the issues of translation and of translatability are general and concern the possibility of mutual intelligibility in many registers and including within a single natural language. Both anthropologists and ancient historians are faced with such problems, where the historians are at a disadvantage in not being able to check their understandings with those whom they are seeking to understand. But faced with seemingly paradoxical statements, beliefs, or practices, we must and can avoid the apparent dilemma (*either* those statements must be rendered in or reduced to our terms *or* we must admit they are strictly incomprehensible) by insisting on the revisability of our existing conceptual framework, especially in relation to such key terms as personhood, agency, causation, and nature. Again, instead of insisting on the dichotomy of literal and metaphorical, we should allow that any term may exhibit what is here called semantic stretch. Moreover, if we accept (as is argued here) that the phenomena or realities described are multidimensional, then the goal of a single definitive translation is a mirage. The open-endedness of translation is no threat to mutual intelligibility but its precondition.

De la possibilité d'une intelligibilité mutuelle

Details Figures References Cited by

HAU: Journal of Ethnographic Theory
Volume 4, Number 2
Autumn 2014

Published on behalf of the Society for
Ethnographic Theory

Article DOI

<https://doi.org/10.14318/hau4.2.010>

Views: 272

Citations: 2

Citations are reported from Crossref

PDF
Help

Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Evans-Pritchard, Edward E. 1956. *Nuer religion*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.

Gladstone, William E. 1877. "The colour sense." *The Nineteenth Century* 2: 360-88.

Graham, Angus C. 1989. *Disputers of the Tao*. La Salle, IL: Open Court.

Henare, Amiria, Martin Holbraad, and Sari Wastell, eds. 2007. *Thinking through things: Theorizing artefacts ethnographically*. London: Routledge.

Heywood, Paolo. 2012. "Anthropology and what there is: Reflections on 'ontology'" *Cambridge Anthropology* 30: 143-51.

Hocart, Arthur M. 1915. "Psychology and ethnology?" *Folk-Lore* 26: 115-37.

Holbraad, Martin. 2012. *Truth in motion*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Holbraad, Martin, Morten Axel Pedersen, and Eduardo Viveiros de Castro. 2014. "The politics of ontology: Anthropological positions." *Fieldights—Theorizing the Contemporary, Cultural Anthropology Online*, January 13. <http://culanth.org/fieldsights/462-the-politics-of-ontology-anthropological-positions>.

Ingold, Tim. 2000. *The perception of the environment*. London: Routledge.

Kuhn, Thomas S. (1962) 1970. *The structure of scientific revolutions*. Revised edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Laidlaw, James. 2012. "Ontologically challenged." *Anthropology of This Century* 4. <http://notpress.com/articles/ontologically-challenged>.

Laidlaw, James, and Paolo Heywood. 2012. "One more turn and you're there." *Anthropology of This Century* 5. <http://notpress.com/articles/turn>.

Latour, Bruno. (2012) 2013. *An inquiry into modes of existence*. Translated by Catherine Porter. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

2014 | *HAU: Journal of Ethnographic Theory* 4 (2): 221-235

Lloyd, Geoffrey E. R. 1970. *Early Greek science: Thales to Aristotle*. London: Chatto & Windus.

———. 1990. *Demystifying mentalities*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

———. 1991. *Methods and problems in Greek science*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

———. 2002. *The ambitions of curiosity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

———. 2004. *Ancient worlds, modern reflections*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.

Mendeley

- Build a library
- Citations
- Bibliography

AutoSave ON | Coronavirus 2020 Spread in Discourse | Dr Mark Perkins

File Home Insert Design Layout References Mailings Review View Help Grammarly Share Comments

Table of Contents | Insert Footnote | Insert Citation | Export as | Style: American Psych... | Mendely Cite-O-Matic | Smart Lookup | Researcher | Citations & Bibliography | Captions | Index | Table of Authorities

Coronavirus 2020: Spread in Discourse

Mark Perkins, PhD
Cambridge UK: Repindex Ltd
The author has worked in Text Analysis for over 20 years.

Contents

Abstract	1
1. Introduction.....	1
2. The Coronavirus Discourse Universe	2
3. The Coronavirus Discourse Stream	3
4. COVID-19 Charts	5
4.1 COVID+CRISIS	5
4.2 COVID+RECESSION.....	5
4.3 COVID+HOPE/FEAR.....	5
4.4 COVID+MILD.....	6
4.5 COVID+CURE	6
4.6 COVID+TREATMENT.....	6
4.7 COVID+VACCINATION	6
4.8 COVID+FAKE	6
5. Fake COVID-19 discourse streams	6
6. COVID-19, China and Trump	8

Page 1 of 15 | 3153 words | Recovered | Focus | 10:28 19/08/2020

When to Publish?

- The flow in your field
- When to release results
- Impact on the field
- Impact on your career

Tam O'Shanter
by
Robert Burns

Tam O'Shanter: A Nordic Tinge and a New Translation

Mark Perkins

- The narrative poem Tam O'Shanter written by Scottish national poet Robert Burns in 1791 is considered a great poem
- It often forms the centrepiece of Burns night, the 25th of January, when Burns' birth is celebrated in many parts of the world
- As a long poem written in Scots, 1,513 words in 228 lines

Motivation

It sounds Swedish!

33	Ah, gentle dames! it gars me greet ,	Ah, gentle dames! it makes me weep,
34	To think how mony counsels sweet,	To think how many counsels sweet,
35	How mony lengthen'd, sage advices,	How many lengthened, sage advices,
36	The husband frae the wife despises!	The husband from the wife despises!

Tam O'Shanter
Robert Burns

Translation
and
Reading

by Mark Perkins

<https://www.nationalgalleries.org/art-and-artists/1961/robert-burns-1759-1796-poet>

Publication Timing

- Burns Night
- 25th January
- So
- Publish early January
- A Preprint
- Inform all interested people
- Maximum impact

Tam - References

* a new translation of Tam o' Shanter, which you will find on Youtube:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o-nBVIHJIAE>

* a monograph on the influence of Old Norse on the poem

* a short article about the translation

* a slide set of the translation

All found here:

<https://hcommons.org/members/markperkins/>

Thanks for Today!

See you the next time!
mark.perkins@mpl-training.com

Mark
Perkins, PhD
MA

- Academic and Business Trainer – International Clients
 - Editing
 - PhD and article reviewing
 - Pakistan, China, Nigeria, EU (Poland)
- Tech company owner – Repindex
- Research Associate, GLOKOR Poland
- Lived in Italy, Czechoslovakia, Sweden (university lecturer)
- Former Head of Teacher Training (English), Folk University of Sweden, Gothenburg
- Phd, MA, LTCL, LRAM
- Trainer and Applied Linguist
- Major: Ancient Philosophy